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SUSTAINABILITY MANAGEMENT,
FINANCE, AND ECONOMICS
IN A CHANGING BUSINESS LANDSCAPE**

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Comparative analysis of sustainable logistics and green approaches: A study in the context of Türkiye and Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

In this era where environmental awareness is increasing rapidly, the integration of sustainable logistics and green approaches is a very important effort. This study carries out a comparative and detailed analysis of the unique geographies of Türkiye and Vietnam. Through the establishment and rigorous review of the relevant literature, the research sheds light on cross-cultural dynamics by guiding the complexities of sustainable logistics practices. The logistics industry, which is an integral part of global trade, is facing increasing pressure to reconcile operational efficiency with ecological responsibility. In this pursuit, Türkiye and Vietnam emerge as intriguing case studies due to their disparate regulatory frameworks and socio-economic contexts. Examining the challenges, motivations, and cultural influences that shape the adoption of sustainable logistics, this study contributes to the broader discourse on environmentally responsible supply chain management. Aimed at practitioners, academics, and policymakers, this research summarizes insights from the theoretical foundations and current scientific contributions. The importance of the work is reflected in its potential to inform industry practice, enrich academic dialogue on sustainable logistics, and guide policy formulation. The analysis illuminates the complex interplay between environmental awareness and operational strategies, leading the logistics industry towards a more responsible and sustainable future.

Keywords: sustainable logistics, cross-cultural comparison, green approaches, environmentally responsible supply chain management.

1. Introduction

In this era where global awareness of environmental problems is increasing rapidly, the integration of sustainable practices emerges as the most important issue among the sectors. In this era of sustainability, industries worldwide are undergoing transformative changes to align their practices with ecological responsibility (Holguín-Veras et al., 2017). Among them, the logistics industry emerges as the cornerstone of global trade and supply chain operations and plays an important role in the efficient transport of goods across borders and continents. The imperative to promote sustainable development and address ecological concerns has led to the inclusion of green approaches and sustainable logistics practices, ushering in a new era of conscious logistics operations (Tang, Liu, & Wang, 2020).

Due to the rapid growth of the global population and the increasing interconnectedness of our global community, resources are becoming scarcer. Hence, it is crucial to prioritize sustainable delivery services, which involve striking a balance between efficient logistics and responsible resource usage. Amid the challenges posed by resource scarcity, increasing environmental degradation, and increasing carbon emissions, the logistics industry is faced with a unique task: to strike a delicate balance between seamless delivery mechanisms and ecologically conscious practices (Sarkis et al., 2011). The multifaceted nature of this effort necessitated a paradigm shift in the traditional approach to logistics. It is necessary to work jointly to go beyond the limits of existing organizations,

conceive cutting-edge initiatives that oppose traditional concepts, and modify practices in a wide context of the international supply chain. This makes it important to restate logistics as a necessary element of sustainability, which involves environmental conservation, financial advancement, and an improved quality of life (Lambert & Schwieterman, 2012). Sustainable logistics practices integrate a number of actions that strive to limit wastage through waste management efforts, practice cost-effective transport by optimizing the usage of fuel, and include the latest technology to refine processes and bring in more efficiency (Ding, Liu, & Zheng, 2016).

Moreover, sustainable logistics constitutes a very important example of a proactive approach towards the adoption of new technologies that coincide with environmental objectives in this period. For example, the integration of electric vehicles appears to herald a transformative change in transport modes, not only increasing efficiency but also contributing tangibly to reducing emissions. For this cause, many businesses favor the moving of automobiles that are more ecological and create less pollutant while having a high worth in terms of sustainability. In addition, the adoption of autonomous systems has the capability to maximize logistics operations and lessen the environmental impact (Holguin-Veras et al., 2021). The importance of sustainable logistics essentially goes beyond operational efficiency and gets to the heart of ecological responsibility. The industry of logistics recognizes its capacity to create positive change and emphasizes the importance of its role in addressing global difficulties. It manages the intricate connection between respectful environmental practices and organizing the logistics process, aiming to progress towards a more sustainable and robust future.

Türkiye and Vietnam, as distinctive nations in the global landscape, navigate the intricate balance between environmental responsibility and economic advancement. Their journeys of growth are underscored by the imperative to harmonize progress with ecological preservation, a challenge accentuated by the global call for sustainability, further underscored by the recent COVID-19 pandemic (Şentürk & Kuyun, 2021; Ürgen-Vorsatz et al., 2015). Both countries share a fervent commitment to economic growth as a way to improve infrastructure development and living standards. However, this pursuit is offset by the ecological cost of increased consumption and industrial expansion, leading to emissions, rapid resource depletion, and environmental pressure (World Bank, 2020; World Bank, 2022). This situation requires a strategic balance between juxtaposition, growth, and protection. The path to modernization brings with it a number of environmental challenges. Urbanization and industrialization strain air quality and natural resources, revealing the urgency of reconciling development with environmental well-being (Nguyen & Trinh, 2018; Nathaniel et al., 2020). The evolving landscape requires serious decisions calibrated to ensure sustainable coexistence. The rapid increase in the population of both countries and the rapid depletion of resources cause major environmental problems. Türkiye and Vietnam can raise awareness of societies by making new initiatives to increase green resource use.

In the midst of these challenges, sustainable logistics is emerging as a conduit to bridge growth targets and ecological imperatives for both countries. Türkiye and Vietnam can optimize their logistics practices while reducing environmental impacts and aligning their development trajectories with environmentally sensitive principles (Sarkis et al., 2011b). This integration paves the way for a holistic approach to address the subtle challenges of contemporary development.

This research undertakes a comparative study aiming to elucidate in detail the factors that shape the adoption of sustainable logistics practices in the logistics sectors of Türkiye and Vietnam. The main purpose of this research is to discover the motivations and

impediments, to disclose the regular techniques, and to clarify the cultural elements that impact the adoption of eco-friendly logistics procedures in two specific contexts. This is beneficial not only for instructional motives but also for those individuals in businesses wanting to make their logistical operations more sustainable. Moreover, the insights gained in this study have the potential to guide policy formulation by aligning economic growth with a wider range of ecological sustainability. With the goal of fostering an environmentally conscious logistics industry, this study strives to connect theory and practice, promoting responsibility.

2. Theoretical Basis

This study's theoretical foundation is an interdisciplinary framework based on literature encompassing green supply chain management, sustainable logistics, and cross-cultural comparisons. Because this study provides a detailed examination of sustainable logistics practices in Türkiye and Vietnam, it is critical to situate the research within the existing theoretical framework. Despite the fact that Türkiye and Vietnam are in very different geographies, the parallels and differences in green supply chain management, sustainable logistics, and cross-cultural comparisons will be investigated. Because both countries are classified as developing, the context will become clearer.

2.1 Sustainable Logistics and Green Supply Chain Management

Sustainable logistics, which is the basis of this study, covers in detail the integration of environmentally responsible practices into various aspects of logistics operations. This encompasses a holistic approach to reducing emissions through efficient route planning, optimizing transportation systems, minimizing waste generation through improved packaging and handling, and increasing resource efficiency in inventory management (Sarkis et al., 2011c). By prioritizing sustainability in their logistics processes, organizations can increase cost-effectiveness and operational efficiency while minimizing their ecological footprint.

Green supply chain management (GSCM), built on the foundations of sustainable logistics, broadens the perspective to cover the entire supply chain network. This approach requires the systematic integration of sustainability principles throughout the entire supply chain lifecycle, from raw material procurement to end-of-life product disposal. It covers green purchasing practices, sustainable distribution strategies, environmentally friendly production processes, and environmentally responsible consumption patterns (Walker et al., 2008). The noble essence of GSCM lies in the understanding that every stage of the supply chain has the potential to contribute to or mitigate environmental impacts.

The integration of these sustainable logistics and GSCM principles is based on the recognition of the profound environmental consequences that supply chain and logistics activities can have. The movement of goods in global markets, while essential for economic growth, is associated with significant resource depletion and carbon emissions. In response to growing concern about climate change and resource scarcity, both industry and academia have recognized the imperative to adopt practices that not only optimize logistics and supply chain processes but also reduce their negative environmental impact (Huang & Han, 2021).

This study examines the application of these intertwined principles of sustainable logistics and GSCM in the specific context of Türkiye and Vietnam. By examining the challenges, approaches, and implications of these practices in different cultural and regulatory environments, the research aims to uncover valuable insights that can inform strategies to promote sustainability, taking into account the unique characteristics of each country's logistics and supply chain environment. In doing so, the study contributes to a

broader understanding of global efforts to achieve both operational and environmental excellence.

2.2 Drivers of Sustainable Logistics Adoption

The adoption of sustainable logistics practices is a multifaceted process shaped by the combination of influences from various economic, organizational, and regulatory domains. Organizations are driven to adopt sustainable logistics practices due to the possibility of major cost savings. The introduction of energy-efficient initiatives, streamlining of transportation routes, and lessening waste output can not only diminish the environment's load but also cut businesses' operating costs significantly. This economic rationale is in line with the principles of long-term financial sustainability and resource efficiency, making sustainable logistics an attractive proposition for businesses that want to increase their competitiveness in the global market (Seuring & Müller, 2008).

Regulatory pressures further emphasize the need to adopt sustainable logistics practices today. National policies and international agreements increasingly emphasize environmental protection and sustainability as key priorities. Organizations must adapt their logistics operations to these evolving regulations to avoid legal repercussions and ensure compliance. Driven by emissions reduction targets, carbon neutrality, or waste management directives targets, these regulatory guidelines shape the operational environment and require the integration of sustainability principles into logistics strategies (Hebaz & Oulfarsi, 2021).

In the field of organizational dynamics, motivations to adopt sustainable logistics extend beyond immediate economic and regulatory factors. Businesses that incorporate CSR objectives into their practices understand the importance of balancing profit with purpose. By fully committing to sustainability, they show stakeholders their commitment to making a positive contribution to the environment, society, and their communities. This helps to build trust and long-term relationships with customers, investors, and employees. Additionally, organizations that integrate CSR objectives into their practices demonstrate their focus on ethical and responsible behavior, which can lead to increased profits. The ethical repercussions of sustainable logistics practices also coincide with the growing awareness of consumers trying to support environmentally responsible businesses. This harmony between organizational values, stakeholder expectations, and sustainable logistics practices strengthens the integration of these practices into core business strategies (Wang et al., 2018).

Moreover, the modern business environment is characterized by an increasing scrutiny of corporate behavior and a greater emphasis on transparency. Organizations are realizing that sustainable logistics practices not only contribute to environmental protection, but also increase their overall resilience by reducing the risks associated with market volatility, resource scarcity, and reputational damage. Due to this, the implementation of sustainable logistics is not simply a reaction to outside forces; it is seen as an educated decision that can enhance strength, bring benefit over other companies, and help contribute to long-term accomplishment.

2.3 Challenges and Barriers

Although sustainable logistics practices can bring about various advantages, many hindrances and issues present themselves when attempting to put such measures into place. These barriers arise in various dimensions encompassing technological, cultural, financial, and organizational factors and collectively shape the complex landscape of sustainable logistics adoption (Sánchez-Flores et al., 2020). Cultural factors significantly influence the

integration and acceptance of sustainable practices within organizations. Cultural norms, customs, and attitudes can facilitate or hinder the adoption of environmentally sound practices. Different perceptions of sustainability among different regions and societies can lead to reluctance or resistance to depart from established practices. Aligning sustainable logistics principles with current cultural paradigms; plays an important role in determining the degree of acceptance and participation among management, employees, and other stakeholders (Seuring & Müller, 2008b).

Technological limitations represent another major obstacle to the seamless incorporation of sustainable logistics practices. While green technologies offer promising ways to reduce environmental impact, their adoption may be constrained by factors such as limited infrastructure, high upfront costs, and technical complexity. The readiness of the technological ecosystem in a given region and the availability of skilled personnel to operate these technologies can further accelerate or completely hinder the integration of sustainable innovations into logistics processes (Ghadge et al., 2020).

Financial considerations pose a major hurdle for many organizations considering the transition to sustainable logistics. While the long-term benefits, such as increased brand reputation and reduced resource consumption, are convincing, the initial investment required to renew existing logistics operations can be substantial. Uncertain return on investment, budgetary constraints, and the need to balance short-term fiscal goals with long-term sustainability goals can prevent organizations from committing to necessary changes (Gong et al., 2019)

Organizational dynamics also play a crucial role in shaping the path to sustainable logistics adoption. Internal resistance from employees' concerns about disruptions to established workflows can adversely hinder the implementation of sustainable practices. Resistance may stem from employee perception that adopting new processes can lead to inefficiency or increased workload. In such situations, open communication is vital for effective change management strategies and addressing these concerns and ensuring participation from all levels of the organization (Walker et al., 2008b). As organizations overcome these multifaceted challenges, it becomes clear that the transition to sustainable logistics is not just a technical effort, but a holistic transformation that requires strategic planning, cultural sensitivity, financial prudence, and effective change management strategies.

2.4 Cross-Cultural Dynamics in Sustainable Logistics

The intercultural dimension brings a unique and complex layer of complexity to the process of adopting sustainable logistics practices, especially when examining the examples of Türkiye and Vietnam. Culture has a tremendous amount of power over how people make decisions, view things, and act in organizations. It can heavily tilt the perspective of sustainability practices and determine how they fit into business frameworks. As such, it can be a vital factor towards having a successful sustainable logistics program (Song et al., 2018).

Comparative studies conducted in different cultural contexts such as Vietnam and Türkiye highlight the profound impact of norms, cultural values, and practices on the implementation and effectiveness of sustainable logistics practices. In Vietnam, for example, deep-rooted cultural values may prioritize long-term intergenerational management of resources and social cohesion. This can create fertile ground for sustainability practices that comply with the principles of conservation of resources and minimum environmental impact. On the other hand, in Türkiye, a country located at the crossroads of Europe and Asia, cultural values and historical influences can emphasize

resourcefulness and adaptability. Understanding how these values intersect with sustainable logistics practices is crucial to developing strategies that fit the cultural fabric of each country (Zeng et al., 2017).

Moreover, cultural differences can permeate various dimensions of adopting sustainable logistics, such as supply chain relations stakeholder engagement, and employee attitudes. The way employees perceive and respond to sustainability initiatives, the dynamics of cooperation and communication in supply chain networks, and the expectations of investors and consumers are all influenced by cultural nuances. Thus, implementing sustainable logistics practices requires a culturally informed approach that acknowledges and accepts these differences (Zeng et al., 2017).

In Vietnam, where Confucian values and collectivism prevail, a stronger emphasis can be placed on social responsibility and community involvement in sustainable logistics efforts. In Türkiye, where Eastern and Western influences are blended, sustainable logistics initiatives may need to align modern approaches with traditional resource management practices. This study, which examines this complex interaction between culture and sustainable logistics in depth, aims to reveal not only the challenges arising from intercultural differences, but also innovative solution opportunities arising from cultural diversity. Ultimately, it is crucial to acknowledge and address these cross-cultural dynamics when comparing and contrasting sustainable logistics practices between Vietnam and Türkiye. Adopting a culturally sensitive perspective, this research can provide nuanced information to facilitate the identification of effective strategies tailored to each nation's different cultural contexts.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

Based on the literature reviewed, this section summarizes the theoretical framework that guides the analysis of sustainable logistics practices in the context of Türkiye and Vietnam. The theoretical lenses chosen provide a comprehensive framework for understanding the complex interplay between economic factors, cultural dynamics, and the adoption of sustainable logistics.

2.5.1 Institutional Theory

Institutional theory is used as the cornerstone of the theoretical framework because of its ability to explain the effects of external pressures on the practices of organizations (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). International agreements, regulatory frameworks, and societal expectations shape organizations' adoption of sustainable logistics practices. By adhering to institutional pressures, organizations signal legitimacy and relevance in their industry (Bansal et al., 2019). This perspective is particularly important in terms of examining how economic and cultural differences in Türkiye and Vietnam affect organizations' responses to sustainable logistics imperatives.

2.5.2 Resource-Based View

The resource-based view strengthens the theoretical framework by emphasizing the important role of organizational resources in adopting sustainable logistics practices (Barney, 1991). This perspective highlights that the capabilities of organizations, including financial resilience, technological investments, and operational flexibility, significantly affect their capacity to successfully implement green practices (Mudgal et al., 2010).

The resource-based perspective in the context of sustainable logistics provides a lens through which the allocation and deployment of resources can be examined. Technological investments, such as incorporating advanced energy-efficient monitoring technologies or transportation systems, require substantial financial commitment. The

ability to allocate resources to these advances is influenced by several factors, including risk tolerance, corporate financial health, and strategic orientation (Gan et al., 2022). As an illustration, those corporations who are economically robust could be in a superior spot to invest in the most current environment-favorable delivery systems, but those with limited funds may have to focus on modest progress. Having the capability to change quickly is another component of the resource-based view which has a bearing on joining sustainable transport procedures. It has agile operational structures and is adaptable, and organizations are better equipped to implement and adapt green practices as the industry environment evolves (Singh & Roy, 2020). The capacity to respond quickly to changes, whether regulatory changes or technological developments, highlights the importance of operational flexibility in the context of sustainable logistics.

Cultural differences and economic inequalities in Türkiye and Vietnam increase the importance of the resource-based approach in this study. These differences can affect the allocation and availability of resources for sustainable logistics efforts. Economic factors such as GDP and industry competitiveness can affect organizations' financial ability to invest in sustainable logistics practices. Moreover, cultural dimensions, such as power distance and uncertainty avoidance, might impact organizations' willingness to take risks and experiment with new green practices (Wang et al., 2021). By integrating the resource-based perspective into the theoretical framework, this study aims to reveal how organizations in Türkiye and Vietnam allocate resources strategically to adopt sustainable logistics practices. The resource allocation lens provides a detailed understanding of the mechanisms by which economic factors and cultural nuances influence organizations' decisions to invest in green logistics solutions.

2.5.3 Cultural Dimensions Framework

The cultural dimensions framework proposed by Hofstede (2009) is embedded in this framework. This lens facilitates a deeper understanding of how cultural differences between Türkiye and Vietnam affect the adoption of sustainable logistics practices. Cultural dimensions such as individualism-collectivism, power distance, and uncertainty avoidance affect individuals' behaviors and attitudes toward sustainability (Trivellas et al., 2020). This framework analyzes the manifestation of dimensions in each country, revealing how cultural nuances shape the integration of green practices.

2.5.4 Technology-Organization-Environment Framework

The technology-organization-environment framework emphasizes the interdependence of organizational practices, technological factors, and external environment dynamics (Baker, 2011). In the context of sustainable logistics, this lens facilitates the investigation of how technological advances and environmentally friendly innovations are aligned with the practices of organizations. It sheds light on how cultural diversity and economic differences in Türkiye and Vietnam affect the diffusion and adoption of sustainable logistics technologies (Holguín-Veras et al., 2020).

The combination of these theoretical perspectives establishes a comprehensive scaffold for the analysis of sustainable logistics practices within the Türkiye and Vietnam contexts. This framework not only elucidates the complex interactions between economic, cultural, and organizational factors but also illuminates the mechanisms through which sustainable logistics practices are adapted, adopted, and diffused across different nations.

3. Methodology

This section summarizes the methodological approach adopted for this study, based on a comprehensive review of the available literature. The purpose of this research was to create an in-depth awareness of sustainable logistics behavior in both Türkiye and Vietnam

by synthesizing ideas, information, and results from prior scholarly articles. The methodology is based on an extensive literature search using electronic databases such as ResearchGate, Emerald (Emerald Insight), Google Scholar, ScienceDirect (Elsevier), and Web of Science. These platforms were chosen because they cover a wide range of scientific articles, peer-reviewed journals, and conference proceedings on sustainable logistics and cross-cultural comparisons. The literature review generally covers studies published from 2018 to ensure the integration of contemporary and current understandings. In the search process, keywords and phrases suitable for the focus of the study such as "green supply chain management", "sustainable logistics practices", "intercultural comparison", "Türkiye" and "Vietnam" were used. This technique enabled a wide variety of pertinent research to be analyzed.

The articles were selected based on their relevance to sustainable logistics practices, cross-cultural comparisons, and the compatibility of the study with the geographical context of Türkiye and Vietnam. The review prioritized research, peer-reviewed articles, and conference articles that provided theoretical frameworks, empirical evidence, and practical information on the adoption of sustainable logistics practices. Articles that did not directly contribute to the research focus or were not published in English were excluded from the review. In addition, a few very rare articles were included, focusing only on regions other than Türkiye and Vietnam, or studies that did not address sustainable logistics practices in selected contexts.

Given the nature of the methodology, the data analysis process involved synthesizing and summarizing the trends, key findings, and perspectives of trends identified in the articles reviewed. The analysis aimed to provide a coherent narrative highlighting the differences, similarities, challenges, and motivations regarding sustainable logistics practices in Türkiye and Vietnam. It is important to note that the methodology of this study was based solely on an analysis of the available literature. The lack of primary data collection, such as interviews and surveys, can limit the depth of insights compared to empirical studies. In addition, despite the rigorous search strategy, there is a possibility that some related articles were mistakenly excluded from review.

4. Results and Discussion

This section presents the synthesized results and discussion from the extensive literature review. The analysis delves into trends, key insights, and findings regarding sustainable logistics practices in contexts specific to Türkiye and Vietnam. Drawing on current research, this chapter aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the common challenges, perspectives, and motivations surrounding sustainable logistics in these two countries.

4.1. Similarities and Differences in Sustainable Logistics Practices

When the literature is examined, both similarities and differences emerge more clearly in the adoption and implementation of sustainable logistics practices between Türkiye and Vietnam. A notable similarity is the growing recognition among organizations in both countries of the importance of integrating environmental considerations into their logistics operations (Sarkis et al., 2020). This shared recognition reflects the global trend towards supply chain management and environmentally sound business practices. However, the existing literature also highlights important differences that affect the course of sustainable logistics in each country. Economic inequalities also play a role, as Türkiye's larger economy and more developed industrial environment offer more opportunities to invest in green technologies compared to Vietnam (Do et al., 2020). Moreover, cultural factors shape the prioritization of sustainability, along with different cultural norms that affect how organizations in each country prioritize and approach eco-

friendly logistics practices (Trivellas et al., 2020b).

4.2.Challenges and Motivations

The literature review highlights the various challenges faced by organizations in both Türkiye and Vietnam in adopting sustainable logistics practices. These challenges include the lack of regulatory incentives, limited resources, and insufficient awareness of the long-term benefits of green logistics (Hsu & Hu, 2008; Jermisittiparsert et al., 2019). Conversely, their motivations to adopt sustainable logistics practices are multifaceted and extend beyond environmental concerns. While environmental responsibility remains an important factor, economic advantages such as cost savings through waste and energy efficiency reduction are also important motivating factors (Gupta et al., 2020). In addition, the expectations of stakeholders, including investors and customers who demand greater sustainability, further encourage the commitment of organizations to integrate environmentally friendly practices (Zhou et al., 2019).

The cultural dimensions of Türkiye and Vietnam affect the adoption of sustainable logistics practices in different ways. Cultural traits such as respect for authority and collectivism in Vietnam can influence corporate decision-making and potentially facilitate alignment with broader sustainability goals. Similarly, cultural values in Turkey can play a role in shaping the willingness of organizations to adopt sustainable practices as part of their core values

The synthesized results highlight the complex interplay between cultural, economic, and regulatory factors in shaping sustainable logistics practices in the context of Türkiye and Vietnam. While economic inequalities can affect resource allocation, shared motivations and challenges highlight the universal importance of adopting eco-friendly logistics strategies. Understanding these dynamics provides valuable information for policymakers, industry practitioners, and researchers who aim to promote sustainable logistics practices in diverse cultural and economic environments. The ongoing discussion delves deeper into these findings, exploring potential strategies to increase motivation, overcome challenges, and promote the adoption of sustainable logistics practices. By contextualizing the results within a theoretical framework, this chapter aims to contribute to the ongoing dialogue on sustainable logistics, thereby informing strategic decisions and promoting a greener and more efficient supply chain in both Türkiye and Vietnam.

5. Implications and Conclusion

This conference article includes a comprehensive review of sustainable logistics practices in specific contexts of Türkiye and Vietnam. Utilizing a literature review approach, this study synthesizes information from existing research to shed light on common perspectives, motivations, and challenges driving the adoption of eco-friendly logistics strategies in these two countries.

The analysis reveals a number of notable findings that contribute to the discourse on sustainable logistics practices. The similarities between Türkiye and Vietnam lie in understanding the importance of integrating environmental considerations into logistics operations. Both countries recognize the importance of balancing economic growth with ecological responsibility, reflecting the broader global trend towards environmentally sound business practices. However, important differences also emerge. Economic inequalities play a huge role in influencing the depth and speed of sustainable logistics adoption; Türkiye's more developed industrial environment potentially offers greater opportunities for investment in green technologies. Cultural factors further shape the course of sustainable logistics, with different norms affecting the prioritization and integration of environmentally friendly practices within organizations.

The information from this study has implications for a variety of stakeholders, from researchers to industry practitioners and policymakers. By understanding common motivations and challenges, organizations can develop strategies that take advantage of economic benefits while addressing environmental concerns. Emphasizing the role of cultural dimensions, the study deeply emphasizes how cultural characteristics shape the approach to sustainability and potentially facilitate its integration with corporate values. For policymakers, this study highlights the importance of considering cultural and economic factors when designing incentives and regulatory frameworks that promote sustainable logistics practices. In addition, the study adds to the academic discourse by providing a comprehensive overview of the dynamics affecting sustainable logistics practices in different cultural and economic environments.

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study. Relying on the available literature limits the depth of insights compared to empirical studies that involve primary data collection. Although efforts have been made to provide a comprehensive literature review, the possibility of omission of some relevant articles cannot be completely ruled out. Future research efforts could extend the findings of this study by using empirical methods such as interviews and surveys to gather first-hand information from logistics professionals in Türkiye and Vietnam. Such primary data collection will provide a more nuanced understanding of the challenges, perspectives, and motivations driving sustainable logistics practices in these contexts.

In conclusion, this conference paper contributes to the ongoing dialogue surrounding sustainable logistics practices by contextualizing key findings within a theoretical framework. By highlighting in detail both the similarities and differences between Türkiye and Vietnam, the study enriches the understanding of how cultural, economic, and regulatory factors intersect to shape organizations' adoption of eco-friendly logistics strategies. The insights gained from this study have the potential to guide policy formulation, inform strategic decisions, and pave the way for a more sustainable and efficient supply chain in both countries.

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